

SOCIAL ANALYSES OF THE MODERNIZATION OF YOUTH CULTURE

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Annotation. This article examines the socio-cultural features of the youth subculture as a new non-traditional aesthetic form of mastering objective reality, an autonomous form of attitude to everything, the search for one's own ethnicity, spiritual and aesthetic identity in a complex globalized transition to a digital society. The purpose of the article is a social analysis of the subculture of youth, in order to understand and realize this phenomenon, it is necessary to study the characteristics and determinants of this informal youth movement. The authors sought to show subculture as a "protest" of the traditional way of life and thought, the formation of a special caste of youth with new traditions and values of artistic culture.

Keywords. Culture, artistic culture, subculture, informal, aesthetic education.

Introduction

In the context of globalization of information technologies, modernization of all spheres of public relations is being carried out, and strategic development goals of the Republic of Uzbekistan are being implemented. The introduction of new digital technologies radically changes the socio-economic and cultural life of the Uzbek people, the renewal of which is most clearly manifested in the lives of young people. In this regard, the study of the universal and national in the spirituality and artistic culture of modern youth has become relevant. Thus, a new generation of boys and girls is growing on the waves of man-made civilization, which distinguishes the behavior of the older generation from the norms, which is the most difficult problem of the relationship between generations, the continuity of tradition and the values of the people.

In modern scientific literature, the artistic culture of youth is considered in the context of the general socio-cultural life of the population, the impact of the industrialization of the country on the ethical and aesthetic norms of youth behavior [16]. Another group of scientists considers the problems of modernization of artistic culture from the point of view of the threat of "Mass culture", including the problem of reaction to the preservation of ethno-confessional identity [17, p. 113]. The third group of sociologists emphasize the

formation of a new "subculture of youth", which originated in Western Europe and the USA [3, p. 460]. This classification of research on modern youth culture allows us to identify the main vectors of research in contradiction of modern and traditional values of society, problems in the continuity of ethno-confessional culture, renewal of traditions and values, in accordance with new realities and challenges, taking into account the preservation of the spiritual heritage of the people.

Such a culturological goal and approach requires a social analysis of the modernization of the youth subculture as part of the general culture of the people. This essentially requires the identification of the essence of the subculture of youth, the peculiarities of popularization among students, which is clearly manifested in modern youth art.

Materials and methods

The materials and methods of this article are the fundamental theories and practical provisions in the philosophical research of social sciences by scientists of the world. The authors focus on the problems of transformation of value-based social attitudes and orientations of youth in ethno-confessional identification in the conditions of man-made civilization. Thus, the article considers such concepts as "artistic culture", "subculture", "national heritage", which is a condition for theoretical understanding and practical reflection of this phenomenon as a subject of research. In the process of social analysis, the authors revealed a peculiar pattern of contradiction between traditional and innovative in social progress, affecting the socialization of youth

In social analyses of this problem, the most important thing is to preserve the ethnic and confessional identity of the people, respect for the traditions and values of the rich culture of the peoples of the region. In this regard, it was natural to apply general scientific and philosophical methods of artistic cognition of the world of youth. The socio-axiological method provides an opportunity for artistic awareness of the psychology of youth in a global digital society. The authors relied on the results of sociological observations and surveys to identify the features of the value aesthetic orientations of the modern generation of social networks.

Results

Subculture as an aesthetic exploration of objective reality. Subcultures are the result of modern industrial progress in public life, the transition from a traditional lifestyle to an electronic society, where digital production has replaced the traditional machine production of products and consumer goods.

Information and communication technologies have come very close to the life of the population, part of the way of life and thinking, an attribute of modernity and backwardness, as the countries of the world have divided into two camps: producers and consumers. All this led to an adjustment of the social appearance of modern man: the youth of Western Europe with a focus on material well-being, profit and capital, and in the East the search for social identity, striving for ethno-confessional morality, which can be argued by the ideas of the World Congress of Philosophers [10].

The peoples of the East have contributed their rich artistic culture to the world spiritual culture, the spiritual heritage of which originated at the dawn of world civilization, careful attitude to music, theatrical art, painting and masterpieces of applied art, writing determines the prospects for the social development of the peoples of Central Asia. The specificity of the artistic culture of the region's population, as it seems to us, is the spirit and ideas of the culture of Islam. The religiosity of artistic creativity provided a flavor of high morality and aesthetic catharsis. The artistic catharsis of works of art is aimed at the collective life of the Muslim community, as a condition of divine tolerance in the form of tolerance. Islamic culture considers the artistic culture of a person as a factor of loyalty to Allah and the great Prophet Muhammad.

The globalization of the socio-economic and cultural life of the peoples of the world naturally affects the socio-cultural life, corrects the traditions and values of youth. Thus, the new non-traditional culture spreading among the peoples of the East is called by scientists as "Mass Culture", a threat to the traditional ethnic way of life and thought. Indeed, in the modern world reality, there are new norms of behavior, lifestyle and thought, changes in traditional values and lifestyle, which can be called an "unconventional", "new" phenomenon in the artistic culture of modernity. However, in the scientific literature, this phenomenon is defined as a youth subculture, the result of the technogenic culture of society.

Social analyses have shown that the theory of subculture put forward by representatives of the Chicago School of Sociology implied new non-standard and non-traditional phenomena in the musical art, since musical art was the basis for the development of the subculture of youth. In fact, the musicians sought extravagant clothes in front of the public, new decorations and performances in front of young people, which became popular among boys and girls. It should also be noted that the realization of their creative abilities is clearly manifested among young people, to show a kind of creative new wave of

artistic expression. In addition, during certain periods, European musicians became popular in the CIS countries, which became an ideal imitation of their idols in art. Thus, the spread of subculture in the region, in its essence, took place under the influence of the rejection of the Soviet and the adoption of a new non-traditional culture of the West as "Mass Culture", the modernization of the norms of ethics and aesthetics of the spiritual culture of youth [5; 13].

We agree with A.A. Androsov that the origin of the youth subculture can be divided into the following groups: passion for music, increased participation in strengthening public order, protection of natural resources, certain sports, interest in philosophical mysticism and others [1]. The popularization of the subculture of youth in its essence reflects the unity of the "influence of social space" for all the youth of the world, that subculture is the result of the "import" of the Western way of life among the peoples of the CIS. An example of this is the fact that the youth movement "Flash Mob", "Hippie", "Kitsch", "Oldies", "Vandal", "Griffith", which originated in Latin America, is found in the cities of Central Asia. It should also be noted that there is no unity of opinion among CIS scientists on the interpretation of "subculture", many are inclined to call "informal" than the youth subculture. We agree with those scientists who argue that civil informal organizations and movements are a natural process of development of civil society. This phenomenon, as it seems to us, can be an indicator of the manifestation of the law of "Denial of denial" of the social political life of society. A similar opinion is found in the research of scientists of the world [4;5; 6]. In this regard, we agree with the classification of signs of youth subculture such as special fashion, which "... is expressed in hairstyles, clothes and accessories; – Language and a special symbolic world; – Music; – Emotionality of behavior; – Aggressive and/or negative attitude towards representatives of other youth subcultures; – Organization of the surrounding social space (specific meeting places, appropriate attributes, in some cases – protection of one's own territory, etc.); – High level of group solidarity; – Indifferent attitude to the political life of society, ignoring generally accepted norms and values, alienation from economic life" [3, p. 463].

Subculture reflects the discontinuity in the continuous historical socio-cultural processes, forming new non-formal cultural values of the youth "modern" and traditional norms and values of the older generation. A similar split in cultural relations, the difference of which is expressed in the mastery of modern scientific and technical achievements, which is easier for young people to master information technologies than the older generation.

Discussion

The main trends in the development of youth subculture come from a modern man-made civilization, the existing mass character devalues traditional values and forms new youth rules of behavior, lifestyle and aesthetic exploration of the world. Therefore, the priority of spiritual and educational work is based on the collective nature of local authorities with family and school, which has created an urgent need for aesthetic education, the formation of youth on high universal and national ideals of morality. In this regard, we stand in solidarity with those scientists who focus on the determinants of S. I. Levikov's youth non-formal culture. He believes that "The youth subculture arises from the need of young people for self-expression, self-affirmation in society and the impossibility, for one reason or another, of satisfying them in a traditional way. In order to assert himself in an unconventional way, a young person should first accept the uniformity of a certain kind of youth subculture. At the same time, it is enough for him to reach a certain age to become a recognized member of an informal youth group, where the path to an adult is forever closed [7].

Subculture is a new reflection of objective reality, aesthetic rejection of the traditional way of life, loss of control by society over ethical and aesthetic education, youth anarchy in the search for spiritual identity. In this regard, we agree with Uzbek scientists who assert subculture as a "Protestant culture" against the traditional ethno-confessional life of society, manifestations of ethical deviance of youth [13, p. 17].

Thus, there is active research on the problems of artistic culture of students, which is difficult to identify the overall picture without social analysis of young people who are outside the walls of education. Non-students form a special community with specific socio-psychological attitudes and social orientations. Thus, as part of non-formal youth movements, there is an activation of girls, striving to achieve certain successes, with a tendency to popularity, ready for antisocial acts and pronounced cynicism. In this regard, it seems to us that the entire education system needs to establish strict educational discipline, a ban on mobile communications in the learning process, violations of which are an educational punishment to increase the university's rating. This idea can be argued by normative acts on improving the artistic culture of the population [11;12].

The research of the formation of the artistic culture of youth in the conditions of the global information society has many factor fields, covering the

entire sphere of socio-economic and cultural life, the problems of socialization and professionalization of personality. In this regard, we agree with those authors who characterize the theories and practices of the formation and development of the artistic culture of youth. They ask serious polls about the degradation of youth culture, which does not give the expected results of imposing artificial ideas of political and ideological patriotism on them [8, p.6; 9, p. 151]. It should be recognized that in recent years, the governments of the CIS countries have made youth policy a priority, and in some situations, there is a fetishization of their interests, which negatively affects their spiritual development.

In some cases, scientists associate subculture with the psycho-cultural processes of the youth environment, that they are painfully going through a transitional age, the mutual understanding of the youth generation with the elders is complicated, in some cases "barricades" are manifested. We find similar approaches in the analysis of non-formal youth movements in the works of I. V. Vlasyuk, E. N. Sitnikova, who assert the duration of youth adulthood in contrast to previous generations [2, p.71]. The transformation of the social appearance of generations has been most fundamentally studied by scientists, according to which each generation inherits social experience from its ancestors, which is called upbringing and education in society [16].

Conclusions

The subculture of youth is an achievement of the democratization of public life in the conditions of a global technogenic civilization, the prosperity of "Mass Culture", the revolution of information and communication technologies. It became a transition from a traditional way of life to an innovative one, from collective to individualism, the manifestations of which are observed in the contradictions of the ethno-confessional way of life in the information liberalization of public life.

Informal youth movements in their essence devalue upbringing and education, which is encouraged by the state youth policy of the CIS countries, fetishization of youth in socio-political life do not give the expected positive results in society. Thus, there was an urgent need to educate young people on the best traditions of the spiritual heritage of the people, to strengthen the educational discipline of students at all stages of modern education. Of particular relevance today are the words of the brilliant educator of the National educator Abdullah Avloni, who proclaimed "Education for us is a matter of life or death, salvation or death, happiness or trouble".

In the development of the artistic culture of youth, they can be a good immunity in preventing manifestations of the subculture of youth, in which administrative "prohibitions" or forceful techniques and techniques should not be allowed. The inclusion of study hours in all educational systems of aesthetic education, an increase in study hours in the higher education system, and the activation of activities of the artistic and creative potential of young people can become a real determinant of the formation of an intellectual youth elite with a high ethical and aesthetic taste for life.

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